

**Synthesis of some New Pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]-
pyrimidine Derivatives and their
Antibacterial Activity**

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OUR interest in the use of *o*-aminonitriles of hetero-
aromatic compounds as precursors for the fused
pyrimidines by their reaction with heterocumulenes
prompted us to investigate the reaction of 3-amino-
4-cyanopyrazole derivatives with aryl isothiocya-
nates. It was reported¹ that when a mixture of
ethyl 5-amino-1-arylpyrazole-4-carboxylate and
aryl isothiocyanate was refluxed in DMF-acetic acid,
1-aryl-4-oxo-5-substituted-phenylpyrazolo[3,4-*d*]-
pyrimidine-6-thiones were obtained. We conducted
the reaction of 3-amino-4-cyanopyrazole derivatives
(1) with isothiocyanates in pyridine at room tempera-
ture and observed that the reaction proceeded
smoothly in pyridine to afford some new 5-aryl-4-
iminopyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine-6-thiones (3a-1)
(Scheme 1). It was also observed that the condensa-
tion of 3-amino-4-cyanopyrazoles with phenyl iso-
thiocyanate in the presence of an equivalent amount
of sodium hydroxide afforded 3-thioureido-4-cyano-
pyrazoles, and on refluxing these compounds in an
organic solvent containing sodium hydroxide, cycli-
sation took place to form the 5-aryl-4-iminopyrazolo-
[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine-6-thiones (3a-1). The com-
pounds (Table 1) were characterised by elemental
analysis, ir, nmr and mass spectral studies. Some
of the compounds¹ were screened for antibacterial
activity against some selected microbes.

Scheme 1

Experimental

The 3-amino-4-cyanopyrazole derivatives were obtained following the reported procedures². M.ps.

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3*

Compd. no.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹
2a	MeS	H	Phenyl	187	66	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂	3 350 (NH), 3 250 (NH), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
2b	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	195	66	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂	3 300 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 210 (C≡N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
2c	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	179	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	3 320 (NH), 3 250 (NH), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
2d	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	185	69	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂ O	3 320 (NH), 3 150 (NH), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
2e	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	175	74	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂ O	3 350 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S), 820
2f	H	H	Phenyl	162	66	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ S	3 400 (NH), 3 300 (NH), 2 250 (C≡N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
2g	H	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	156	66	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	3 400 (NH), 3 310 (NH), 2 240 (C≡N), 1 590 (C=N), 1 150 (C=S)
2h	H	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	145	63	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SCl	3 390 (NH), 3 280 (NH), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 570 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
2i	H	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	152	62	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ SO	3 410 (NH), 3 300 (NH), 2 200 (C≡N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S), 825
2j	H	H	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	140	63	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ SO	3 420 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 220 (C≡N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S), 825
3a	MeS	H	Phenyl	208	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂	3 350 (NH), 3 100 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S), 700
3b	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	225	73	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂	3 360 (NH), 3 100 (s, NH), 2 995 (C-H), 1 650 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S), 700
3c	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	238	72	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	3 340 (NH), 3 100 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3d	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	234	68	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS ₂	3 350 (s, NH), 3 100 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3e	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	192	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS ₂	3 400 (s, NH), 3 100 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S), 825
3f	MeS	H	Phenyl	280	63	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ S	3 400 (s, NH), 3 210 (NH), 2 900 (C-H), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
3g	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	290	65	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	3 390 (s, NH), 3 190 (NH), 2 900 (C-H), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170
3h	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	292	75	C ₁₁ H ₈ ClN ₂ S	3 430 (s, NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 995 (C-H), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170
3i	MeS	H	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	284	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS	3 400 (s, NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 995 (C-H), 1 600 (C=N), 1 770 (C=S), 825
3j	MeS	Ph	Phenyl	230	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ S	3 400 (NH), 3 250 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
3k	MeS	Ph	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	198	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	3 400 (NH), 3 240 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
3l	MeS	Ph	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	212	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClO ₂ S	3 390 (NH), 3 210 (NH), 1 590 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)

*Satisfactory elemental analyses have been obtained for all the compounds.

m/z: 2a 135(*M*⁺ 100), 108(66); 3a 289(*M*⁺ 67), 231(18), 135(100), 93(66); 3c 323(*M*⁺ 57), 325(18), 290(4), 265(4), 169(100), 171(33), 127(69); 3f 243(*M*⁺ 15), 210(32), 185(100), 135(65), 108(27).

are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was ascertained by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Hewlett-Packard 5995 spectrometer at 70 eV.

5-Aryl-4-iminopyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine-6-thiones (3a-1): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) and pyridine (5 ml) was kept at room temperature for 48 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into water (100 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (~4 ml). The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised.

3-(1-Aryl-3-thioureido)-4-cyano-5-methylthiopyrazoles (2a-j): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) and powdered sodium hydroxide (0.01 mol) in dimethylformamide (20 ml)

was stirred till the pungent smell of isothiocyanate disappeared (1.5 h). The mixture was diluted with water (100 ml) and acidified. The resulting solid was purified by crystallisation from ethanol.

Cyclisation of 3-thioureido-4-cyanopyrazoles. Preparation of 5-aryl-4-iminopyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine-6-thiones (3a-1): 3-(1-Aryl-3-thioureido)-4-cyanopyrazole (0.005 mol) was dissolved in a solution of sodium hydroxide (0.005 mol) in ethanol (20 ml). The yellow solution obtained was heated for 2 h, then diluted and acidified. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised.

Results and Discussion

All the pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidines showed ir bands at 3 420-3 350 (=NH), 3 220-3 100 (ring

NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 580 (NH-C=S) and 1 180-1 240 cm^{-1} (C=S). The nmr spectrum of a representative sample (3c) showed signals at δ 2.5 (3H, MeS), 2.8 (1H, br, imino NH), 4.9 and 7.15 (1H, br s each, ring NH), and 7.3-7.6 (4H, m, Ar-H). The mass spectrum showed peaks at m/z 325(18%), 323(M^+ : 57), 290(4), 265(4) and 127(69). These data are compatible only with a 5-aryl-4-iminopyrazolo-pyrimidine structure (3c) assigned to the product.

The thioureido derivatives were found to deposit lead sulphide on warming with alkaline lead acetate solution and gave a positive ammoniacal silver nitrate test which are characteristic reactions of disubstituted thioureas⁹. In the ir spectrum, bands due to $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching vibrations were seen and they exhibited fragmentation typical of thiourea derivatives. The mass spectrum of 4-cyano-3-(1-phenyl-3-thioureido)pyrazole did not exhibit a strong molecular ion peak at m/z 243. Instead, it was dominated by two major fragments at m/z 135 and 108. No other fragments were seen above m/z 135. The two major fragments could arise by the rupture of the thiourea under electron impact.

Antibacterial activity: Some of the compounds were screened *in vitro* for antibacterial activity against some selected microbes by agar diffusion method⁴. For this screening, bacteria⁵ isolated from aquatic environments as well as from coconut husk were used. Of the eight compounds tested for antibacterial activity, the following were found to be active (diameters of the inhibition zone 1.2-3.0 cm at concentrations 50-500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$): 4-cyano-3-(1-phenyl-3-thioureido)pyrazole, 3-(1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-thioureido)-4-cyanopyrazole, 4-imino-5-*p*-tolylpyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine-6-thione, and¹ 4-imino-6-methylthio-5-*p*-tolylpyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine.

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